

necessary, they were incubated at 30°C to avoid adverse effects of atmospheric low temperatures.

The varieties were classified by dormancy (time to 80% germination) as follows: nondormant, seed dormancy broken 10 d after harvest (DH); weakly dormant, dormancy broken 40 DH; moderately dormant, dormancy broken 60 DH; and strongly dormant, more than 60 d to break dormancy.

Long dormancy (80 to 100 d) was found more in medium and late maturing varieties (see table).

Exceptions were the early maturing Dular with moderate dormancy (60 d) and very late maturing Baok with no dormancy. *♠*

Dormancy in 39 rice varieties, Hooghly, West Bengal, India.

Maturity group	Nondormant (10 d)	Weak dormancy (40 d)	Moderate dormancy (60 d)	Strong dormancy (80-100 d)
Early aus	Satika	—	Dular	—
Early aman	CR205	EMH3 CR201 AC517 Dudhkati CR205	Badkalamkati 65 Churnakati Malsira Jhulur Asuda Badkalamkati T-1	Dudhraj KXI-36 Sankarkalma
Medium aman	—	Rupsail	Bhasamanik Kalma 222 Dudhsar Nagra Indrasail	Latisail Patnai 23 Jhingasail SR26B Radhunipagal Badsabhog
Medium-late and late aman	Baok	NC1281	Gabura OC1393	NC678 Kumargore Tilakkachari Achra FR43B

Effect of gamma-radiation on germination and seedling growth

N. Kumar and S.S. Malik, Haryana Agricultural University, Regional Research Station, Uchani (Karnal), India

Four rice varieties — Sonalee, Prasad, IR36, and Tetep — and the F₂ of Sonalee/Prasad, Sonalee/IR36, and Sonalee/Tetep were irradiated with 30 and 40 krad gamma rays from ⁶⁰Co source and germinated in the incubator at 37°C.

Germination and root shoot length were measured at 10 d. All treatments reduced germination (see table). Lowest germination was shown by Sonalee at 30 krad (63%) and 40 krad (59%). IR36 exhibited maximum germination. Germination in Sonalee/Prasad was higher than that of either parent but was less in Sonalee/IR36 and Sonalee/Tetep.

Root and shoot length decreased as irradiation increased in all populations; the lowest values were for Tetep with 40 krad. Radiation affected roots more than it did shoots.

The hybrid Sonalee/Prasad had shorter roots than either parent; the

Effect of radiation on germination and seedling growth. Karnal, India.

Genotype	Germination (%)	Root length (mm)	Shoot length (mm)
<i>No radiation</i>			
Sonalee	81	13.60	7.10
Prasad	90	14.27	12.30
Sonalee/Prasad	100	12.64	11.09
IR36	95	15.89	11.24
Sonalee/IR36	81	15.45	13.77
Tetep	100	14.46	12.10
Sonalee/Tetep	81	16.85	14.83
<i>30 krad</i>			
Sonalee	63	4.67	9.81
Prasad	85	4.34	8.00
Sonalee/Prasad	90	8.23	9.20
IR36	90	10.93	11.46
Sonalee/IR36	72	9.88	11.12
Tetep	72	7.92	10.92
Sonalee/Tetep	72	9.77	8.37
<i>40 krad</i>			
Sonalee	59	1.95	4.94
Prasad	72	3.24	6.26
Sonalee/Prasad	85	2.57	5.59
IR36	85	3.62	5.31
Sonalee/IR36	70	6.95	7.21
Tetep	81	1.31	1.86
Sonalee/Tetep	70	3.86	4.87

hybrid Sonalee/Tetep had longer roots than either parent. In Sonalee/IR36, root length was intermediate.

Shoots of Sonalee/IR36 and

Sonalee/Tetep populations were longer than those of the parent varieties; in Sonalee/Prasad, shoot length was intermediate. *♠*